
MECHANISM FOR DEVELOPING POSITIVE QUALITIES IN PRIMARY PUPILS

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Yusupova Firuza Ikromovna

Primary teacher of school 20 in samarkand district.

Annotation.

This article provides information on the development of positive qualities in elementary school students, the development of mental abilities, and what methodologies to teach a pupils in launcher classes.

Today, there is a question of preparing qualified, qualified personnel for our society that can implement the development of advanced science and technology in all aspects. Preparing pupils for work at the current stage of school education is one of the most important tasks of the growing generation in education and upbringing, as labor is the basis of any development and development process. Preparing students for work in elementary schools is a manual labor based on their interests, inclinations and opportunities. In this regard, the labor education process is aimed at developing pupils' knowledge, labor, moral, aesthetic, economic, ecological, and mental opportunities for this age in specific work processes.

The Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan also adopts separate provisions on labor. For example, "Everyone works hard, chooses a free career, and works in fair working conditions. (Model 37) All citizens who are hired have the right to rest. . . . (Article 38) Everyone has the right to receive social education when he or she grows old, loses his or her employment skills, as well as loses his or her child and in other cases referred to in the law. . . . (Model 39)" examples of such legal norms.

Similarly, the emphasis on labor education is also focused on public education. Including primary education, each class has been designated to organize one hour of vocational education a week. The objective of the primary schools' vocational education is to "create a space for pupils' professional preparation by teaching them the basics (technology) of work processes, occupations, and harmonizing them with the choice of professions so that they can be formed as perfect individuals."The educational objective of vocational education is also great,

namely, to “develop high moral qualities, industriousness, patriotism, humanitarianism, and entrepreneurship in the process of acquiring pupils’ skills.” Both the responsibilities of vocational education teachers and the demanding implementation of these tasks play an important role in the development of young people as perfect people in modern times.

There are several strategies that teachers can use to develop positive relationships with pupils. These include providing structure in the classroom, teaching with enthusiasm and passion, having a positive attitude, incorporating humor into lessons, making learning fun, using student interests to your advantage, incorporating storytelling into lessons, showing an interest in their lives outside of school and more.

In addition to this, parents and educators across cultures value character strengths as they promote the well-being of themselves and others. These strengths are positive qualities individuals have that are reflected in their thoughts, feelings, and actions. Some examples of character strengths include creativity, curiosity, gratitude, kindness, perseverance and more.

In addition to this, Charles Starkey, Associate Professor of Philosophy studies emotion theory and moral psychology. He says that character traits are determined by our values but that emotions also play a huge role. In short, kids need emotional intelligence and to notice and be influenced by positive character traits in others. The other critical thing is consistency. This was highlighted to me when my own kids started school. I remember feeling as if many of the positive traits I’d worked so hard to nurture were starting to slip. I knew kids with different upbringings and values would challenge their beliefs and behavior. However, the thing it emphasized the most was a need to incorporate social and emotional learning and character education in the classroom.

Moreover, there are given some solutions to develop positive qualities in primary school children:

- Be around positive role models.

It sounds obvious really. When you liken a child’s brain to a sponge that soaks up information, the significance of modelling is clear. It is important to note that the younger a child is, the more adaptable they are. Their thought processes and behaviors are more pliable which makes it important for them to be exposed to positive role models early. Apart from being a great role model yourself, point out the positive traits of those around you. Highlight and have conversations about good things other people do. Take time to discuss what they did, why it was

positive and how it made others feel. This is a great way for kids to notice and understand what good behavior looks like.

- Acknowledge and appreciate good behavior.

Kids love to please the important people in their lives. When they show positive character traits make sure to acknowledge their good behavior. Showing you appreciate what they did or said helps kids identify what you like and encourages more of it. Teachers can use a resource that teaches, acknowledges and rewards positive character traits.

- Read books that help build character.

Kids are often bombarded with negative and conflicting information that challenges their standards. A good book with lessons about character can help to counter these outside influences. Create a fun routine at bedtime where you read together and discuss topics addressed in the book. Teachers use books in the classroom to enhance lessons and find them useful as prompts for writing activities. Check out our reading list for great picture books.

- Ask your school to incorporate Social and Emotional Learning (SEL).

This is huge! Historically, schools have had little to do with character education but that is thankfully changing. Educationalists now acknowledge that emotional intelligence plays an important part of success in many aspects of life including academic achievement.

Educational activities are not only knowledge processes for a junior high school student provides an opportunity not only for high-level development, but also for the development of individual characteristics. During junior high school age, the formation of a child's personality continues. Reader the success of the school in the development of his next psychological development and personality will be a completely positive basis. This can result in a child starting to realize his place in his family, class studying and other communities on his own.

The transition to new activities is a new attitude toward the student's own basic functioning and it is made. A sense of duty begins to grow in it. That he is obliged to read and he is his duty that the specified rules and requirements must be met. Self-real feeling like a reader, there is a need for good reading in it. The moral minds of junior high school students undergo important changes during grades IV, and moral qualities, knowledge and I and perceptions are significant and the child begins to understand himself. It is good-for-bad, which is unique although he doesn't know the characteristics, but he feels like "I." that it is his duty, his purpose, his ability to do it, that it is his duty to perform the tasks assigned to the house.

He understands. Children of this age are intrigued by the knowledge of a large number of environmental events that are not included in the school program. These interests are also reflected in the child's interest in creative games, which are often ignored.

Such games reflect his sense of social interests, emotions, anxiety for the team. Curiosity demonstrates the broad mental activity of children of junior high school age

is a form. To be a person who needs God, openness, confidence, and readiness to carry out all his assignments are broad social duty motivations and effective conditions for responsibility so that he knows the importance and importance of reading.

Interests in the early years of school education, especially interests in acquiring knowledge, intellectual interests develop significantly. Psychologists say the program Interest in some facts, lone events that are separated from other things, is generated. In addition, in grades III - IV, the communication and interaction between causes, laws, events interests will develop to find out the dependence.

Teachers pay enough attention to students' work in their work, prepare specifically for the work lesson, monitor students' every movement with dignity and observation, treat them individually is desirable. Tests conducted by F.I.Ivashchenko show that reading in conditions where students do not believe in themselves, they are primarily caused by the following reasons:

- a) failure to follow the principle of consistency in reading;
- b) by letting students know that they do not have the strength, i.e. by putting out excessive demand;
- c) some teachers, parents, and at the same time, the student power of classmates, due to distrust of memory skills and insights;
- d) Main by intimidating and punishing such readers for receiving bad grades. The upbringing of Israel is strongly related to the upbringing of thought and emotions.

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